

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Double-pentagon silicon chains in a quasi-1D Si/Ag(001) surface alloy

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Supplementary Figure 1. **LEED patterns before and after Si deposition.** LEED patterns ($E = 40$ eV) of the clean Ag(001) substrate before (left panel, 1×1) and after (right panel, 3×3) 0.8 ML Si deposition with the sample held at 490 K. Yellow arrows indicate the integer order spots; blue arrows the fractional order spots along the $+X$ and $+Y$ directions.

Supplementary Figure 2. **STM image of a low coverage area.** **a** Empty state STM image ($20 \times 20 \text{ nm}^2$, $V_s = +1 \text{ V}$, $I = 2 \text{ nA}$) showing a Ag(001) terrace adjacent to 3×3 domains. **b** Line profile along the black arrow shown in **a**. **c,d** Filled state STM image and line profile ($V_s = -1 \text{ V}$, $I = 2 \text{ nA}$). Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 3. **Bulk truncated structural models.** Full set of optimized bulk truncated schematic models of the Si/Ag(001)-(3 × 3) surface, side and top views. Topmost three or four layers are shown. Unit cells are indicated by red squares/rhomboids.

Supplementary Figure 4. **Surface alloy structural models.** Full set of optimized surface alloy schematic models of the Si/Ag(001)-(3×3) surface, side and top views. Topmost three or four layers are shown. **a** Models based on a single Ag missing row substrate geometry, i.e. $2/3$ ML Ag coverage. **b** Surface alloy models having Ag coverage above $2/3$ ML. **c** Surface alloy models having Ag coverage below $2/3$ ML. The most stable model, SA-8Si-2Ag, is also referred to as SA-DPC. Unit cells are indicated by red squares/rhomboids.

Supplementary Figure 5. **Phase diagram for full set of models.** Surface formation energies of Si/Ag(001)-(3 × 3) models, relative to that of the clean Ag(001) surface. **a** Bulk-truncated models, as presented in Supplementary Fig. 3. **b** Surface-alloy models, for higher Ag coverage, as presented in Supplementary Fig. 4a,b. The shaded area indicates the range of stability of the BT-8Si-a model. **c** Surface-alloy models, for lower Ag coverage, as presented in Supplementary Fig. 4c. The BT-10Si data is shown again for comparison. The most stable model is SA-8Si-2Ag (SA-DPC). Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 6. **PDOS calculations.** Projected density of states calculation of the SA-DPC (SA-8Si-2Ag) model. The peak at +0.6 eV arising from surface Ag atoms is responsible for the apparent shift of the STM image for larger positive biases. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 7. **Large-scale high-resolution bias-dependent STM images.** Experimental $7.5 \times 7.5 \text{ nm}^2$ STM images collected at 80 K with tunneling current $I = 20 \text{ nA}$, at the bias indicated. White squares highlight the 2.6 nm areas reported in Fig. 3.

Supplementary Figure 8. **SXRD fits for full set of models.** Surface x-ray diffraction fits (χ^2) to experimental data in Leandri et al[1] for the Si/Ag(001)-(3 × 3) models shown in Supplementary Figs. 3 and 4. The best fit is found for the SA-8Si-2Ag (SA-DPC) model. Different shadings reflect the same groupings used in Supplementary Fig. 5.

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- [1] C. Léandri, H. Oughaddou, B. Aufray, J. M. Gay, G. Le Lay, A. Ranguis, and Y. Garreau, Growth of Si nanostructures on Ag(0 0 1), *Surface Science* **601**, 262 (2007).